

BIG-MRI: Breast Imaging Group MRI Challenge:

Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

BIG-MRI: Breast Imaging Group MRI Challenge

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

BIG-MRI

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Breast cancer screening programs vary in supplemental modalities like tomosynthesis or MRI, which remain primarily diagnostic rather than routine, with inconsistent breast density notification across countries. Recommendations from European Society Of Breast Imaging (EUSOBI) support supplemental MRI screening for women with dense breasts and high risk individuals to improve early cancer detection, yet implementation is uneven, and validated tools for individualized risk stratification within this cohort are lacking [1,2].

Most protocols do not systematically integrate MRI-based risk assessment, contributing to missed cancers in higher-risk women and overdiagnosis in lower-risk groups. At the same time, widespread MRI screening is constrained by high costs, contrast administration, longer scan times, technical and logistical limitations, so MRI has remained largely excluded from population-level screening pathways [3]. Advances in AI now offer an opportunity to mitigate some of these challenges by extracting richer, quantitative information from MRI and clinical information to support individualized risk estimation. In particular, AI models that accurately predict 2- and 5-year breast cancer risk in women eligible for MRI according to existing guidelines (for example, high-risk or extremely dense-breasted women) could enable tailored screening intervals and modality choices, potentially reducing unnecessary imaging, shortening exam protocols, and lowering overall costs while improving outcomes in breast cancer care [4].

While breast cancer detection-a foundational step-has been extensively studied through public challenges and datasets, progress in risk stratification remains limited by the scarcity of suitable, publicly available datasets for short and long-term predictions.

This challenge addresses that gap by releasing a large, multi-center cohort of women eligible for MRI screening per guidelines (e.g., very high-risk or extremely dense breasts) for 2- and 5-year incident breast cancer risk.

By empowering the research community to explore this topic and develop robust AI models, we will drive

meaningful progress in MRI-based risk stratification, establishing the foundation for clinically relevant benchmarking that can be widely adopted, extended, and referenced across the literature.

We will release a dataset comprising over 3500 de-identified breast MRI exams from a very high-risk screening cohort at Radboudumc (2000–2024), including DCE T1 pre- and post-contrast sequences and linked clinical covariates such as age, cancer detection date, gene mutations, personal/family history, and prior benign biopsies.

The dataset will be distributed via Hugging Face in NIfTI format alongside a de-identified clinical table, supported by existing ethical approvals for public release.

A held-out test set of approximately 1900 exams from a similar high-risk population at the Netherlands Cancer Institute will be reserved solely for blinded evaluation of submitted models along an additional test-set from Radboudumc.

Participants will compete in two parallel tracks via the Grand Challenge platform:

Track 1 (MRI-only): Pure image-based risk prediction using DCE-MRI sequences alone.

Track 2 (MRI+clinical): Multimodal risk prediction incorporating MRI and provided clinical covariates.

Both tracks will predict absolute 2- and 5-year incident breast cancer risk per woman, evaluated on the blinded held-out test set. Primary leaderboard ranking will combine:

- Time-dependent AUC-ROC at 2- and 5-year horizons (with confidence intervals).
- Harrell's C-index over full follow-up, accounting for censoring.

An average normalized ranking across these discrimination metrics will determine final leaderboard positions within each track separately. Calibration metrics may be reported for the models to support clinical interpretation but will not influence rankings.

The Breast Imaging Group, with established expertise in breast MRI, AI-driven risk modeling, and clinical validation, has successfully organized the widely recognized DeepBreath MICCAI workshop for the past two years and co-led last year's ODELIA challenge for breast cancer detection. This upcoming challenge will directly build on these past initiatives and is planned to be hosted by the DeepBreath 2026 workshop. Addressing a critical gap with a significantly large multi-center, multi-vendor dataset, it leverages the successes of the DeepBreath and ODELIA challenges to actively engage MICCAI's AI-for-radiology community. The challenge is named BIG, reflecting both the expertise of the Breast Imaging Group and the large size of the dataset unmatched by previously released public datasets. It features dual tracks (MRI-only and multimodal), survival-aware metrics (C-index, time-dependent AUC, decision curves), and an external test set for rigorous, clinically interpretable benchmarking, advancing time-to-event AI and personalized breast cancer screening.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Breast MRI, Breast Cancer, Risk Prediction

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge introduces a unique dataset and task formulation that bring three layers of novelty to the field of breast MRI research. First, it releases one of the largest breast MRI datasets derived from a screening population-Dutch women eligible for supplemental MRI according to national guidelines. In contrast to most public breast MRI datasets (such as Duke-Breast-Cancer-MRI on TCIA), which consist of retrospective diagnostic or preoperative cases with known malignancies, this dataset represents real-world screening exams. Second, the challenge addresses the clinically pivotal yet underexplored task of risk prediction, formulating 2-year and 5-year incident cancer risk estimation problems. This dual-horizon design enables participants to explore both short-term (personalized screening) and longer-term (population-level prevention) implications of their models. Finally, by offering two complementary tracks: image-based and multimodal (image + clinical). The challenge allows evaluation of AI solutions across scenarios where only imaging data or combined clinical-imaging information is available, fostering generalizable and interpretable advancements in MRI-based risk stratification.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The challenge includes two tasks addressing breast cancer risk prediction over 2-year and 5-year horizons. MRI-only risk prediction uses DCE-MRI to derive image-based risk scores, enabling individualized screening intervals and supporting the development and validation of imaging biomarkers. Multimodal risk prediction combines MRI with clinical covariates to support risk-adapted screening approaches and inform population-level prevention.

Short-term (2-year) predictions are intended to guide near-term screening and imaging decisions within MRI-eligible cohorts, while longer-term (5-year) predictions support strategic surveillance and prevention planning.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

Deep-Brea3th 2026: 3rd Deep Breast Workshop on AI and Imaging for Diagnostic and Treatment Challenges in Breast Care

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Based on participation statistics from our previous ODELIA Challenge, we conservatively estimate that the proposed challenge will attract more than 120 participants. The ODELIA Challenge attracted 95 registrants from 24 countries. Considering the substantially larger dataset, together with the high relevance and growing interest in breast cancer risk stratification, we anticipate that most ODELIA participants will re-engage, in addition to attracting researchers from the broader breast imaging community and the established Deep-Breath community. Several former ODELIA teams have already expressed informal interest in continued participation, providing further confidence in exceeding the projected number of 120 participants.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, we plan to have at least one publication from the challenge results.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

No

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team ([miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de](mailto:micca-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de)) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The HuggingFace for dataset download. Potentially, we may consider Zenodo for long-term archiving should the logistical circumstances permit. Grand Challenge for the model submissions, evaluation etc. On-site requirements include wifi, projector, laptop, microphone, pointer, loud speakers.

TASK 1: Image-Based Risk Prediction

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

This task focuses on estimating short- and mid-term breast cancer risk directly from dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI, motivated by the growing evidence supporting MRI use in high-risk and dense-breast populations. From a biomedical perspective, MRI captures functional and structural tissue characteristics associated with cancer development that are not fully reflected in traditional risk factors and remain underexplored. Technically, the task challenges participants to develop robust image-based learning methods that extract predictive representations from T1-weighted images while accounting for variability in anatomy and acquisition. The envisioned impact is the identification of reproducible imaging biomarkers that support personalized MRI-based screening and improve understanding of imaging phenotypes associated with future cancer risk.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

short term risk prediction, image-based risk prediction, breast cancer risk, personalized screening, population-based prevention

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Nika Rasoolzadeh, Radboud University Medical Center, the Netherlands

Tianyu Zhang, PhD, Radboud University Medical Center, the Netherlands

Xin Wang, the Netherlands Cancer Institute, the Netherlands

Jonas Teuwen, PhD, the Netherlands Cancer Institute, the Netherlands

Henkjan Huisman, Prof., Radboud University Medical Center, the Netherlands

Ritse M. Mann, MD, PhD, Radboud University Medical Center, the Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Nika Rasoolzadeh (Nika.Rasoolzadeh@radboudumc.nl)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, Ritse M. Mann is part of the organizing team of the two tasks above as an interventional breast radiologist and principal investigator of the Breast Imaging Group (BIG).

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time

event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026 conference and Deep-Breath 2026 workshop.

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Grand Challenge (grand-challenge.org). We are in communication with the Grand Challenge support team and will be submitting our application to their platform alongside this application.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

Not available yet, will be created as part of the grand-challenge.org webpage. To be done after proposal acceptance.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Yes, participants are free to perform any curation, pre-processing, or pre-training steps as they see fit, but transparency and reproducibility are mandatory. Every step of the workflow must be documented in detail in the submitted manuscript, including all data curation and pre-processing procedures. If external datasets are used, they must explicitly identify them and describe how the data were integrated or curated. Full code submission is required to ensure that results can be fully reproduced. Only models that meet these rigorous documentation and reproducibility standards, while also demonstrating strong predictive performance and clinically meaningful risk estimates, will be considered valid submissions.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding

(private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants are encouraged to train their models primarily using the data provided by the challenge. If external datasets are used, this is allowed only under the strict conditions outlined for transparency and reproducibility: participants must clearly describe the cohort, characteristics, and any curation of the additional data in their submitted manuscript. All steps involving external data-including integration, pre-processing, and annotation-must be fully documented, and participants must submit all code to ensure results are reproducible.

Additionally, participants should be prepared to engage in open communication after the challenge, to address potential questions or clarifications that may arise during the writing of the challenge paper. Only models that adhere to these standards for documentation, reproducibility, and transparency will be considered valid submissions.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

A cash prize will be awarded to the top-ranking team. Depending on sponsorship availability, the second and third place teams may also receive cash prizes. All top three teams will additionally receive honorary award certificates during the DeepBreath workshop.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top 3 performing teams will be publicly announced. Their results will be presented at MICCAI 2026 and included in the challenge review paper. All participants are welcome to submit a manuscript to the DeepBreath 2026 workshop, subject to the workshop submission deadline.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

An embargo time of 1-2 years will apply, to ensure that the general overall publication describing the purpose and top results of the challenge can be published first. The top 3 team, with up to 2 authors per team, will be included as co-authors of this publication, with the rest listed as "BIG-MRI Challenge group", following, e.g., <https://doi.org/gjxt dw>. During the embargo period, participating teams agree not to publish analyses or results derived from the challenge dataset, nor to release model weights, code, or derived outputs that could facilitate independent publication based on this dataset prior to the official challenge publication. The embargo is intended to ensure a coordinated and fair scientific release of the dataset and benchmarking results through the primary challenge publication.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Submissions will be made via Docker container. Details about the structure, submission guidelines or any necessary templates will be provided. Participants must also submit a manuscript (approximately 4–6 pages) describing their method, including all pre-processing, curation, pre-training, and any use of external data, along with the training and evaluation results. The top 3 teams will additionally be required to share their complete code with the challenge organizers to ensure reproducibility and transparency.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Teams can submit a maximum of 3 times on a small subset of the test dataset for pre-evaluation, and only once for the final submission on the full test set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website opening: April 1-10, 2026

Release of training data: June 15-30, 2026 (a portion of data may be released earlier for the teams to start working on their solutions)

Pre-evaluation/first phase submission opens: July 15, 2026

Final submission opens: July 22, 2026

Evaluation and results (including receiving and checking code of top 3 teams): August 21, 2026

Challenge Day: during the MICCAI Conference (4-8th October), during the Deep-Breath workshop day.

All updates and announcements regarding the challenge and the data will be communicated via our website and social media channels. Before the launch of the challenge the timeline will be optimized ensuring fairness for all participants.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval has been obtained from Research Committee of Radboudumc (CMO-Radboudumc) allowing the data to be used for the public challenge. Details of the ethics approval can be provided if necessary.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The organisers will provide any necessary scripts or templates (docker or otherwise) to ensure clear and proper participation through the Grand Challenge platform. Additionally, a preprint or documentation about the dataset required for proper participation will be shared.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The top 3 teams are required to submit their code for verification, along with a manuscript clearly documenting all steps taken, the data used, methods, and results to promote transparency and reproducibility. During the embargo period, teams are not permitted to publicly release code, model weights, or derived outputs based on the challenge dataset. Upon publication of the primary challenge manuscript, teams are strongly encouraged to make their implementations publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There are no conflicts of interest. Before and during the challenge, only the organising team will have access to the images and labels in the test set.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Screening,Diagnosis,Research,Prevention

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Women eligible for supplemental MRI examinations during screening.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Women undergoing MRI during screening program based on clinical risk factors in the Netherlands.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The images will be given as NIfTI files containing all 2D slices of various sequences of the MRI scan, one for pre-contrast and two or more post-contrast ones. The corresponding information about the sequence will be provided.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No other information related to the patients themselves will be provided as the aim is for the methods to predict risk based on only the images.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The images correspond to the breast/chest region, shown in MRI data

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants are required to submit a Docker image containing a single model capable of predicting individual 2-year and 5-year breast cancer risk. The challenge cohort consists of women undergoing MRI as part of a screening program based on clinical risk factors in the Netherlands. The target of the algorithm is the predicted risk, along with the approximate timing of diagnosis when future cancer is predicted, enabling assessment of both

overall risk and temporal accuracy of predictions. This provides a clear focus for algorithm development while supporting evaluation of both risk probability and time-to-event performance.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Robustness, Integration in workflow, Calibration, Discrimination

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The training set and the test set originates from the Radboud University Medical Center (RUMC), acquired using two Siemens MRI scanners with field strengths of 1.5T and 3T, including models such as Prisma_fit, Skyra, Avanto, and Symphony [5]. The portion of the test set from the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) was acquired using Philips MRI scanners with field strengths of 1.5T and 3T, including models Achieva, Achieva dStream, and Ingenia.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

RUMC data: imaging data includes clinically obtained T1 weighted dynamic contrast enhanced breast MRI scans consisting of one pre-contrast acquisition and at least one post-contrast acquisition (but may include several timepoints) and the associated subtraction image of peak enhancement. Contrast administration is performed after the pre-contrast sequences in a dose of 0.1 mmol/kg at a flowrate of 2.5-4 ml/s, usually via a cubital vein. Temporal resolution is in general around 90 seconds. Spatial resolution is variable and ranges between 1.4 x 1.4 x 3 mm and 0.8x0.9x0.9 mm. Specific scan protocols can be found in :

<https://aapm.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/mp.12079>. No other sequences are provided.

NKI data(additional test set): Imaging was predominantly acquired with fat suppression, and image orientation was primarily coronal. Acquisition matrix sizes range from approximately 320 × 320 to 800 × 800. In-plane spatial resolution varies from approximately 0.6 mm to 1.1 mm, while slice thickness ranges from about 1.2 mm to 2.3 mm. Flip angles are mainly 10° and 12°. Echo times are short, typically ranging from approximately 1.3 ms to 2.3 ms.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Training and test set are from RUMC. An additional test set is provided by NKI.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Clinical teams that include expert radiologists have been involved in the data acquisition in both centres.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case refers to one MRI examination/study for one patient which includes the pre and post contrast and subtraction images.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The training dataset (publicly available) will contain 3000 cases. For the pre-evaluation phase a testset of 500 cases (publicly available) is curated. For the final testing a hidden testset containing 1900 cases from NKI along 500 cases unpublished cases from RUMC will be available. (final quality checks are currently being performed on the datasets)

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

The training set is largely annotated (about 80%), while annotation of the test sets is still in progress (about 30%).

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The dataset is designed to support robust model development and fair evaluation. The training set provides a large cohort for learning, while the test set is multi-center and multi-vendor, including both unpublished RUMC cases to match the training population and a completely independent NKI cohort to assess generalization. This split ensures that algorithms are evaluated on data reflecting real-world variability in scanners, sites, and patient populations.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The dataset reflects real-world breast cancer screening populations. The class distribution follows the natural prevalence of cancer within the cohort, ensuring that algorithms are developed and evaluated under realistic conditions. Training/validation/test sets maintain realistic event rates from multi-center, multi-vendor Dutch cohorts. Test includes unpublished RUMC cases (matched distribution) and independent NKI cohort (external validation).

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All data will be new data, published just in advance for the challenge, so it will be seen for the first time at the time of the challenge.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The reference “annotation” for this challenge is the clinical outcome of breast cancer diagnosis within the 2-year and 5-year horizons. These labels are derived from patient follow-up records rather than image annotation. No manual or in silico image annotation is required. For training and validation cases, the outcome labels are provided to participants. For the test set, the outcome labels are kept hidden for evaluation.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

No additional manual annotations were performed specifically for this challenge. As a result, no separate annotation instructions, annotator training, or software-specific training phases were required. The same data extraction and curation procedures were applied consistently across the training, validation, and test sets.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All labels are derived from existing clinical, histological, and pathological records associated with the MRI datasets of Breast Imaging Group obtained from RUMC, NKI with the efforts of expert radiologists and researchers and Netherlands Comprehensive Cancer Organisation (IKNL).

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

None

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

To protect patient privacy, all data were anonymized by removing patient-identity information. The original DICOM images were converted to the NIfTI format for consistency. The dataset may contain both fat-saturated and non-fat-saturated sequences, and variations in spatial resolution (voxel spacing) are possible across images. Given these inherent variations, participating teams are expected to investigate and implement appropriate preprocessing steps tailored to their methods.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The outcomes rely on curated clinical records (cancer diagnosis dates) rather than manual image annotations. Main error sources include clinical record inaccuracies (5-10% miscoding/missing diagnoses), curator extraction discrepancies (2-5%), and temporal uncertainties from variable follow-up intervals, diagnosis delays (3-12 months), and censoring ($\pm 6-18$ months event timing uncertainty). These low-magnitude errors are uniformly distributed across training, validation (RUMC), and independent test (NKI) sets, representing standard longitudinal cohort variability handled via censoring and time-dependent metrics.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Other relevant sources of error include variability in MRI acquisition protocols across centers and vendors, variability in patient-level clinical characteristics within an otherwise comparable MRI screening population. These factors may introduce systematic variability in the imaging data but reflect real-world screening conditions. Such variability is present across training, validation, and test sets and is intentionally retained to support evaluation of model robustness and generalizability.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Area under curve (AUC): primary metric used for ranking

Harrell's concordance index (C-index): secondary metric

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Algorithm performance will be primarily assessed using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) for 2-year and 5-year breast cancer risk prediction. AUC is chosen as it reflects the ability of a model to discriminate between individuals who will and will not develop cancer across all decision thresholds and is robust to class imbalance typical of screening populations [6,7]. The final ranking score will be computed as the average of the 2-year and 5-year AUCs, ensuring balanced performance across both prediction horizons.

To assess time-to-event performance, Harrell's concordance index (C-index) may be reported as a secondary metric, evaluating whether predicted risk scores correctly reflect the relative timing of cancer occurrence. Secondary metrics are reported for additional characterization and do not affect the final ranking.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The final performance score for ranking is calculated as the unweighted average of the 2-year and 5-year AUCs . Algorithms are ranked in descending order based on this final score. In the event of ties, the higher 2-year AUC is used as a tie-breaker.

Ranking Scheme (Pseudo-code):

For each submitted algorithm:

Compute AUC_2y on all test cases

Compute AUC_5y on all test cases

FinalScore = (AUC_2y + AUC_5y) / 2

Rank all algorithms in descending order of FinalScore

If FinalScore is equal:

Rank higher the algorithm with higher AUC_2y

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions with missing or invalid predictions for one or more test cases will be considered incomplete.

Algorithms are expected to generate valid predictions for all required test cases and both prediction horizons.

Submissions that fail to produce complete results will not be eligible for ranking.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking uses the average of 2-year and 5-year AUCs to ensure balanced evaluation across both prediction horizons. AUC reflects the model's discriminative ability and is robust to class imbalance, making it clinically meaningful and easy to interpret. This scheme provides a simple, fair, and reproducible way to compare algorithms.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The challenge primarily uses discrimination and ranking metrics to evaluate algorithm performance. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) is used to assess the ability of algorithms to distinguish between patients who will or will not develop breast cancer within the 2-year and 5-year horizons. Confidence intervals for AUC are computed using bootstrapping, providing robust uncertainty estimates without assumptions about the underlying distribution.

For time-to-event evaluation, Harrell's concordance index (C-index) is used to quantify how well predicted risk scores correspond to the relative timing of cancer occurrence, accounting for censored follow-up. No parametric assumptions are required for either metric, making these methods suitable for the heterogeneous, multi-center data.

This statistical approach ensures robust, reproducible, and clinically meaningful assessment of both overall risk prediction and temporal accuracy.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of algorithm performance estimates will be assessed using percentile bootstrapping on the test set. Because some patients contribute multiple exams, all resampling procedures will use patient-level clustered bootstrapping to prevent leakage.

For each submitted algorithm, the AUCs at the 2-year and 5-year horizons will be recomputed in each bootstrap sample to derive 95% confidence intervals. Confidence intervals for Harrell's concordance index (C-index), where applicable, will be computed using the same clustered bootstrap procedure. This non-parametric approach provides robust uncertainty estimates without relying on distributional assumptions while accounting for the correlated structure of the data.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across test cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

The variability of algorithm performance across individual test cases is assessed by computing the standard deviation (SD) of case-level predicted risks relative to observed outcomes. Optionally, the interquartile range (IQR) may also be reported to provide a robust measure of variability less sensitive to outliers [7]. This allows assessment of how consistently the algorithm performs across the full test cohort.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Variability of rankings is assessed using bootstrap resampling of the test set, recomputing the average AUC for each algorithm at each iteration, and analyzing how frequently algorithms occupy each rank. This quantifies the stability of the leaderboard and indicates whether differences in rank reflect true performance differences or random variation in the test data.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Differences in performance between algorithms will be assessed using statistical hypothesis testing on the primary score (defined as the mean AUC across the 2-year and 5-year horizons). A paired patient-clustered bootstrap test will be applied.

In each of 1,000 bootstrap iterations, patients will be sampled with replacement, retaining all exams per sampled patient. For each resample, the primary score will be computed for both algorithms, and the distribution of score differences across bootstrap samples will be used to derive a 95% confidence interval and p-value. A difference will be considered statistically significant if the confidence interval of the performance difference does not include zero.

To control for multiple comparisons, formal hypothesis testing will be restricted to comparisons against the top-ranked algorithm (or top K algorithms) within each track. The Holm-Bonferroni method will be applied to control the family-wise error rate at $\alpha = 0.05$.

This approach accounts for the fact that predictions are correlated across the same test cases and does not rely on parametric assumptions. Secondary metrics such as Harrell's C-index can be compared similarly if desired.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Participants are expected to handle missing or incomplete data in the training, validation, and test sets as part of their algorithm design. No imputation or preprocessing is imposed by the challenge; participants may choose appropriate strategies such as imputation, model-based handling, or exclusion of missing features, provided that all steps are clearly documented in the submitted abstract and final manuscript.

The test set will contain the same types of missingness as the training set, ensuring that models are evaluated on realistic clinical scenarios.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

All statistical analyses were performed using Python, leveraging libraries including NumPy for numerical computation, SciPy for statistical testing, and scikit-learn for machine learning algorithms.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Further analyses, including assessments such as absolute calibration risk, clinical utility decision curves, and patient subgroup analyses of the available covariates (e.g. genetic mutation, family/personal history, etc.) may be conducted after the challenge and included in the paper challenge. Where time-to-event and censoring times are available, we will include survival-aware secondary analyses using IPCW-based time-dependent AUC at 2 and 5 years and, optionally, integrated AUC over the follow-up window.

TASK 2: Multimodal Risk Prediction

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

This task focuses on breast cancer risk prediction through the integration of MRI with clinical covariates—such as age, genetic mutations, family or personal history, and prior cancer detection—reflecting real-world risk assessment where imaging complements clinical factors. Biomedically, multimodal integration aims to improve risk estimation by jointly capturing tissue-level imaging signatures and patient-level risk determinants. From a technical perspective, the task encourages the development of methods for multimodal data fusion, including handling heterogeneous feature types, missing data, and differing scales. The anticipated impact is the development of clinically relevant risk models that enable personalized screening and inform population-level prevention strategies.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

short term risk prediction, multi-modal risk prediction, breast cancer risk, personalized screening, population-based prevention

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Nika Rasoolzadeh, Radboud University Medical Center, the Netherlands

Tianyu Zhang, PhD, Radboud University Medical Center, the Netherlands

Xin Wang, the Netherlands Cancer Institute, the Netherlands

Jonas Teuwen, PhD, the Netherlands Cancer Institute, the Netherlands

Henkjan Huisman, Prof., Radboud University Medical Center, the Netherlands

Ritse M. Mann, MD, PhD, Radboud University Medical Center, the Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Nika Rasoolzadeh (Nika.Rasoolzadeh@radboudumc.nl)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Same as task 1.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some

modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026 conference and Deep-Breath 2026 workshop.

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Same as task 1.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

Same as task 1.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Same as task 1.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Same as task 1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Same as task 1.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Same as task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Same as task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Same as task 1.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Same as task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Same as task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference

to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Same as task 1.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Same as task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Same as task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Same as task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education

- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Screening, Diagnosis, Research, Prevention

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Same as task 1.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Same as task 1.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The images will be given as NIfTI files containing all 2D slices of various sequences of the MRI scan, one for pre-contrast and two or more post-contrast ones. The corresponding information about the sequence along the clinical annotation table will be provided.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

A clinical annotation table containing age, gene mutations, family or personal history, and cancer detection dates will be provided. Other than this table no additional information regarding each patient will be released.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The images correspond to the breast/chest region, shown in MRI data

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Same as task 1.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Robustness,Integration in workflow,Calibration,Discrimination

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Same as task 1.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Same as task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Same as task 1.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Same as task 1.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case refers to one MRI examination/study for one patient which includes the pre and post contrast and subtraction images along with corresponding clinical covariates.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Same as task 1.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

Same as task 1.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Same as task 1.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Same as task 1.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Same as task 1.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Same as task 1.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Same as task 1.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Same as task 1.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

None

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Same as task 1.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Same as task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Same as task 1.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Same as task 1.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Same as task 1.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Same as task 1.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Same as task 1.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Same as task 1.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Same as task 1.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Same as task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Same as task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Same as task 1.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Same as task 1.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Participants are expected to handle missing or incomplete data in the training, validation, and test sets as part of their algorithm design. Missing data may occur in clinical covariates for the multimodal task (e.g., family history, prior cancer, genetic data) or, rarely, in imaging metadata. No imputation or preprocessing is imposed by the challenge; participants may choose appropriate strategies such as imputation, model-based handling, or exclusion of missing features, provided that all steps are clearly documented in the submitted abstract and final manuscript.

The test set will contain the same types of missingness as the training set, ensuring that models are evaluated on realistic clinical scenarios.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Same as task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Same as task 1.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

1. Marcon, M., Fuchsjäger, M. H., Clauser, P., & Mann, R. M. (2024). ESR Essentials: screening for breast cancer - general recommendations by EUSOBI. *European radiology*, 34(10), 6348–6357. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-024-10740-5>
2. Kilburn-Toppin, F., Allajbeu, I., Healy, N., & Gilbert, F. J. (2025). Supplemental Screening With MRI in Women With Dense Breasts: The European Perspective. *Journal of breast imaging*, 7(2), 131–140. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jbi/wbae091>
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5. Dalmış, M.U., Litjens, G., Holland, K., Setio, A., Mann, R., Karssemeijer, N. and Gubern-Mérida, A. (2017), Using deep learning to segment breast and fibroglandular tissue in MRI volumes. *Med. Phys.*, 44: 533-546. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mp.12079>
6. Adam Yala et al. ,Toward robust mammography-based models for breast cancer risk.Sci. Transl. Med.13,eaba4373(2021).DOI:10.1126/scitranslmed.aba4373

7. Omoleye, O. J., Woodard, A. E., Howard, F. M., Zhao, F., Yoshimatsu, T. F., Zheng, Y., Pearson, A. T., Levental, M., Aribisala, B. S., Kulkarni, K., Karczmar, G. S., Olopade, O. I., Abe, H., & Huo, D. (2023). External evaluation of a mammography-based deep learning model for predicting breast cancer in an ethnically diverse population. *Radiology: Artificial Intelligence*, *5*(6), e220299. <https://doi.org/10.1148/ryai.220299>

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A